

CAROTENOIDS DETERMINATION IN THE GONADS OF ATLANTIC BLUEFIN TUNA (*Thunnus thynnus* L.)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the first investigation on the carotenoids composition in the gonads of wild Atlantic bluefin tuna (ABT) *Thunnus thynnus*. The objective of this study was to investigate the carotenoids composition of the gonads, at pre-spawning stage, of Atlantic bluefin tuna (ABT) *Thunnus thynnus*, with the aim to obtain a greater knowledge of the bluefin reproductive cycle at a specific tissue molecular composition level, and to provide new data for the possible formulation of specific broodstock diets for the aquaculture of this endangered species. Moreover since tuna eggs are also widely consumed raw, the knowledge on their carotenoids composition is important considering the positive effects of these micronutrients in our diet and of a precise knowledge of the food composition and quality. Astaxanthin was the main carotenoid detected in the samples investigated with an average content of 7.4 µg/g, w/w; β-cryptoxanthin and β-carotene were also detected in small amounts. Astaxanthin chiral isomers were also directly separated on a chiral column and a distribution of respectively (3*S*,3'*S*) 13.1%, (3*R*,3'*S*) 47.8%, (3*R*,3'*R*) 8.4% astaxanthin isomers in the gonads of wild tuna samples was determined for the first time.

KEYWORDS: Atlantic Bluefin tuna, gonads, carotenoids, astaxanthin chiral isomers

INTRODUCTION

The Atlantic Bluefin Tuna (ABT), (*Thunnus thynnus thynnus* L.), is one of the most commercially valuable wild fish species in the global markets. In the wild, sexual maturity in ABT is achieved at 3-5 years of age in the Eastern Atlantic-Mediterranean Sea stock (Corriero, Karakulak, Santamaria, Deflorio, MSpedicato, Addis, Desantis, Cirillo, Fenech-Farrugia, Vassallo-Agius, De la Serna, Oray, Cau, Magalofonou, & De Metrio, 2005). Spawning of ABT in the Mediterranean sea takes place from May to July (Corriero, Desantis, Deflorio, Acone, Bridges, De la Serna, Megalofonou, & De Metrio, 2003).

Due to global massive overfishing, bluefin tuna has been seriously endangered; therefore the development of a proper aquaculture industry for bluefin tuna appears to be the only way to both satiate the great demand for sushi and sashimi and to conserve the wild stocks of this historic fish (Mylonas, Da la Gandara, Corriero, & Rios, 2010; Masuma, Takebe & Sakakura, 2010). In captivity, almost all fishes exhibit reproductive dysfunctions like failure to undergo oocyte maturation, ovulation and spawning as a result of captivity-induced stress and the lack of some essential dietary components in the diet (Watanabe & Vassallo-Agius, 2003). Gonadal development and fecundity are affected by certain essential dietary nutrients, especially in multiple spawner species like bluefin tuna. The carotenoid content of broodstock diets has been reported to be important for normal development of fish embryo and larvae; in fact, the role of the carotenoids during the oocyte maturation, the fertilisation of ovules, egg respiration and egg quality,

embryo development, increased hatchability and better larval survival seems to be very relevant (Schiedt, 1998; Izquierdo, Fernandez-Palacios & Tacon, 2001; Bjerkgeng, 2008). The metabolism that takes place naturally in food chains as to be understood, if the appropriate carotenoid is to be chosen as a feed additive. The objective of this study was therefore to investigate for the first time the carotenoids composition of the gonads, at pre-spawning stage, of Atlantic bluefin tuna (ABT) *Thunnus thynnus*, with the aim to obtain a greater knowledge of the bluefin reproductive cycle at a specific tissue molecular composition level, and to provide new data for the possible formulation of specific broodstock diets for the aquaculture of this endangered species. Moreover since tuna eggs are also widely consumed raw, the knowledge on their carotenoids composition is important considering the positive effects of these micronutrients in our diet (Kritchevsky, 1999; Landrum & Bone, 2001; Van Poppel & Goldbohm, 1995; Britton & Khachik 2009) and of a precise knowledge of the food composition and quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

HPLC-grade solvents, organic solvents and reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). β -carotene, lutein and β -cryptoxanthin were purchased from Extrasynthese (Genay, France). Astaxanthin standards were purchased from CaroteNature (Lupsingen, Switzerland).

Materials and carotenoids extraction

ABT gonads were collected at their pre-spawning stage, from fifteen wild female Atlantic bluefin tuna of similar maturity stage, during the summer 2010 spawning season, captured in the Mediterranean sea. The calculated average gonadosomatic index (GSI) was 4.52. The wild fish were immediately dissected after being caught and the gonads were frozen. About 10 g of each gonad sample was homogenized using an Ultra Turrax in an ice bath with 15 mL of acetone under dim light several times until the samples turned white. The combined acetone extracts were concentrated by roto-evaporation under reduced pressure until less than 5 mL volume remained. 15 mL of methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether (MTBE) and 5 mL of distilled water were then added to facilitate aqueous/organic phase separation. The MTBE phase was collected, washed with distilled water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and 0.1% w/w of BHT was added to prevent oxidation; the MTBE phase was then evaporated to dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen. The extracted carotenoids were resuspended in 2 mL of methyl-*tert*-butyl-ether (MTBE), prior to HPLC analysis.

Carotenoids analyses

The carotenoids extracts were analysed using an HPLC-PDA Shimadzu system equipped with two LC-10AD-Vp pumps, a SCL-10A-Vp system controller, a SPD-M10Avp photodiode array detector and a Rheodyne injector with a 20 μ L loop. An LCMS-2010 Shimadzu mass detector was also used with an atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) interface operating in a positive ionization mode. A YMC 30 analytical column (YMC Europe, Schermbeck, Germany) with 5 μ m C-30 reversed-phase material (250 x 4.6 mm i.d.), including a precolumn (YMC 30; S-5 μ m, 10 x 4.0 mm i.d.) was used. The mobile phase consisted of a binary gradient of methanol/methyl-*tert*-butyl ether/water, MeOH/MTBE/H₂O (83:15:2; v/v/v) (A) and MeOH/MTBE/H₂O (8:90:2; v/v/v) (B), starting with 0% B, maintaining 0% B for 20 min, followed by a linear gradient to 100% B in 5 min, maintaining 100% B for 5 min, then re-equilibrating the column to initial B *conc.*, at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min; chromatograms were recorded at 476 nm and UV-Vis spectra were recorded in the range of 250-650 nm. The mass spectrometer conditions were: APCI positive; nitrogen as the nebulizer gas at flow rate of 2.5 L/min; acquisition range of 200-650 amu.

Carotenoids were identified by comparison with standards and from their spectral characteristics. Each extract was analysed in duplicate. HPLC quantification was carried out using the external standard method.

Astaxanthin optical isomers analysis

The chiral analysis of the gonads extracts was performed with the same Shimadzu system previously described in section 2.3; in this case a CHIRAL PAK IC, 250 x 4.6 mm i.d. and 5 μ m particles, (Daicel

Chemical Industries, Ltd.- Chiral Technologies Europe, Illkirch, Cedex, France) was used; the mobile phase was composed of methyl-*tert*-butyl ether, MTBE 60% (A) and acetonitrile, ACN 40% (B) with an isocratic elution, and at 1 mL/min flow rate. The chromatograms were also recorded at 476 nm and the PDA and MS conditions were the same as described above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carotenoids determination

Carotenoids are lipid-soluble pigments with important antioxidant properties in physiological conditions (Caris-Veyrat, 2008). Some carotenoids are widely employed as colorant in the feed industry, like astaxanthin in the salmonoids and crustaceans aquaculture. In fish, carotenoids are deposited in several types of tissues and organs such as skin, flesh, gonads, intestine, kidney, liver and only in small amount in the brain. Moreover, geometrical and optical carotenoid isomers are distributed selectively in different tissues of fish (Osterlie, 1999). The distribution of carotenoids in fish is primarily the result of specific dietary habits, absorption, metabolic transformation, life stages and the fish physiological state (Hosokava, Okada, Mikami, Konishi, & Miyashita, 2009). ABT in the wild usually have a diet composed of mackerel, squid, sardines and anchovies. This paper presents the first investigation of the carotenoid composition in the gonads at pre-spawning stage, of wild Atlantic bluefin tuna. Fig. 1 shows the HPLC-PDA chromatogram recorded at 476 nm of a typical carotenoids extract of the gonads of wild Atlantic bluefin tuna, obtained using a C30 column. It is clearly evident that, at around 7.5 min, is present a main peak which has been fully characterized as astaxanthin (3,3'-Dihydroxy- β,β -carotene-4,4-dione), by the comparison with its relative standard and also by its UV-vis and MS spectra.

Figure 1. HPLC-PDA chromatogram on a C-30 column of a typical carotenoid extract of the gonads of Atlantic bluefin tuna recorded at 476 nm. Peak 1: astaxanthin.

Fig. 2, shows the mass spectra APCI (+) of the peak characterised as astaxanthin; in particular, it is evident the peak at 597 amu corresponding to the protonated molecular ion $[M + H]^+$ and the peak at 579 amu corresponding to the loss of one water molecule $[M + H - 18]^+$.

Figure 2. Mass spectra APCI (+) of the peak (1) relative to astaxanthin, detected in the gonads of Atlantic bluefin tuna.

Interestingly, Fig. 3 shows (A) the extracted ion mass chromatogram (EIC) at 553 amu, where it is evident a peak with retention time of around 22 min and (B) its relative mass spectra APCI (+) showing the peak of the protonated molecular ion $[M + H]^+$ at 553 amu, which has been characterised as β -cryptoxanthin (β, β -Caroten-3-ol). In fact, β -cryptoxanthin is only present at very low concentration and a clean UV-vis spectra has not been obtained from the HPLC-PDA chromatogram. Similarly, it was also obtained an extracted ion mass chromatogram (EIC) at 537 amu for a peak with retention time around 25 min, with its relative mass spectra APCI (+) showing a peak at 537 amu, which could be assigned to β -carotene (β - β -carotene). Also in this case, it has not been possible to obtain a clean UV-vis spectra from the HPLC-PDA chromatogram, because β -carotene seem to be present in a very low amount.

Figure 3. Extracted ion (EIC) mass chromatogram APCI (+) (A) at 553 amu of the carotenoid extract of the gonads of Atlantic bluefin tuna and Mass spectra (B) of the peak at retention time around 22 min, attributed to β -cryptoxanthin.

Therefore, the main carotenoid detected in the wild bluefin tuna gonads extract was astaxanthin, with an average content of $7.4 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{g/g}$, w/w. During the period that precede spawning physiological changes are induced by endocrine regulations and it is not known whether the carotenoids are transferred to the ovaries directly from the diet through the digestive tract, or whether they are relocated from other tissues *via* carrier lipoproteins (Schiedt, 1998). The nutritional requirements for antioxidants increase during the reproductive season. Interestingly, eggs quality has also been directly correlated to their lipid composition; in fact, eggs considered to be of a better quality had a higher content of total n-3 fatty acids (Brooks, Tyler & Sumpter, 1997). The possible lipid peroxidation can be reduced by the protective antioxidant effect of some polar carotenoids, like astaxanthin (McNulty, Byun, Lockwood, Jacob, & Mason, 2007). Diet formulations are very important for the aquaculture of fish species and various researches have indicated that the required quality and quantity of dietary components like carotenoids may vary according to the species. In aquaculture-raised eggs from adult Chinook salmon astaxanthin was determined at a concentration of $4.12 \mu\text{g/g}$, w/w, (Li, Tyndale, Heath, & Letcher, 2005). In Artic charr fed astaxanthin as the only carotenoid supplement, the relative abundance of astaxanthin was 64-79% of the flesh carotenoids, whereas astaxanthin comprised less than 5% of the total carotenoids of the ovaries, and idoxanthin was the main ovary carotenoid, independently of the fish sex (Bjerken, Hatlen & Jobling, 2000). The dominant carotenoid in the gonads of various natural feed sea urchins species, was echinenone, (Chen, Xiang, Lau, Peng, Qju, & Chen, 2010). Astaxanthin was also the main carotenoid in the gonads of various scallop species, (Miki, Yamaguchi & Konosu, 1982). In yellowtail, soft-dry pellets were used and astaxanthin was found to be the determining factor for good egg quality, and dietary astaxanthin in striped jack was found to increase fecundity (Verakunpiriya, 1997; Vassallo-Agius, Imaizumi, Watanabe, Yamazaki, Satoh, & Kiron, 2001; Watanabe & Vassallo-Agius, 2003). Interestingly, we have carried out a preliminary investigation (Unpublished results) on the carotenoids composition in the gonads of five farmed female Atlantic bluefin tuna samples which were fed a diet composed of a mix of mackerel, squid and a 2 % addition of paprika; although its known that the carotenoids composition of paprika is mainly composed of β -carotene, capsanthin esters and capsorubin esters, we did not detect any of these carotenoids in the carotenoids extract of the gonads of farmed female atlantic bluefin tuna, which instead selectively accumulated astaxanthin ($3.3 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{g/g}$, w/w) probably deriving from the mackerel source (Unpublished results).

The selective accumulation of astaxanthin in the eggs of Atlantic bluefin tuna reported in this work could be useful in a better understanding of the tuna biological reproductive cycle and in the formulation of astaxanthin enriched diets for the aquaculture of this species.

Astaxanthin optical isomers separation

Astaxanthin possesses two identical asymmetric atoms at C-3 and C-3' making possible three optical isomers with all-*trans* configuration of the chain: 3*S*,3'*S*, 3*R*,3'*S*, and 3*R*,3'*R*. Fig. 4, shows the chemical structures of the three astaxanthin stereoisomers. The distribution of the isomers in natural astaxanthin sources derives from the different biological organism that synthesizes them, and differs from that of the synthetic product. Moreover, geometrical and optical carotenoid isomers are distributed selectively in different tissues of fish (Osterlie, 1999).

Figure 4. Structures of *R/S* isomers of all-*E*-astaxanthin: 1 all-*E*-3*S*,3'*S*-astaxanthin; 2 all-*E*-3*S*,3'*R*-astaxanthin; 3 all-*E*-3*R*,3'*R*-astaxanthin.

In this study astaxanthin chiral isomers were also directly separated on a chiral column and a distribution of respectively (3*S*,3'*S*) 13.1%, (3*R*,3'*S*) 47.8%, (3*R*,3'*R*) 8.4% astaxanthin isomers in the gonads of wild bluefin tuna samples was determined for the first time, as it is shown in fig. 5.

Figure 5. HPLC-PDA chromatogram showing the direct astaxanthin chiral isomers separation on a CHIRAL PAK IC column of the carotenoid extract of the gonads of Atlantic bluefin tuna recorded at 476 nm.

Peak identification: 1 all-*E*-3*S*,3'*S*-astaxanthin; 2 all-*E*-3*S*,3'*R*-astaxanthin; 3 all-*E*-3*R*,3'*R*-astaxanthin.

This is important in view of a trend to include untraditional astaxanthin sources in fish fed and could be also useful to distinguish farmed fish species from wild ones. For example, it was shown that in the flesh of wild salmon preferentially the (3*S*,3'*S*) astaxanthin isomer is accumulated (Megdal, Craft & Handelman, 2009), and that the astaxanthin isomer ratios in flesh of rainbow trout fed different carotenoid sources is similar to the distribution present in the diet itself (Moretti, Mentasti, Bellagamba, Luzzana, Caprino, Turchini, Giani, & Valfrè, 2006). Since enantiomers are known to have different physiological properties

knowledge about the uptake and distribution of the different astaxanthin isomers in the organism is important (Grewe, 2007).

The separation of astaxanthin enantiomers reported in this work is of interest since astaxanthin could be used as functional food additive in the feed industry of the tuna species.

CONCLUSIONS

The presence of carotenoids in animal tissues reflect their sources along the food chain and the selective accumulation in the different body tissues of different carotenoids is also a consequence of specific metabolic pathways and functions. The metabolism that take place naturally in food chains as to be understood, if the appropriate carotenoid is to be chosen as a feed additive. Carotenoids have been associated to numerous health benefits and, in most fish species, carotenoids have also been associated with improved rates of fertilization, eggs quality, hatching and larval survival.

Values obtained from wild sample specimens were evaluated as optimum quality parameters on which to base the formulation of an "ad hoc" broodstock diet. Since nutritional factors greatly affect the reproductive performance of fish, the selective accumulation of astaxanthin in the gonads of Atlantic bluefin tuna reported in this work together with its enantiomers distribution could be useful in a better understanding of the tuna biological reproductive cycle and in the formulation of appropriate astaxanthin enriched broodstock diets for the aquaculture of this specie which is seriously endangered by global massive overfishing. Moreover, since tuna eggs can be consumed raw, and considering the importance of the carotenoids in our diet, the knowledge of their composition in those micronutrients becomes interesting.

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